

The Effect of Ion-pairing on the Solvolytic Aquation of Chloropentaamminecobalt(III) Ion in the Presence of Malonate and Succinate Anions

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The rate of solvolytic aquation of chloropentaamminecobalt(III) ion has been measured in aqueous medium in the presence of malonate and succinate anions at 40°, 45° and 50°. The rate accelerating effect of malonate and succinate has been ascribed to the more reactive ion-pairs and the rate and association constants of the ion-pairs have been calculated. The rate constants for the formation of the carboxylate complexes by the entry of the outer sphere associating anions have also been evaluated. The activation parameters of the aquation reaction of the ion-pairs and of the other reaction path-ways and enthalpy, entropy and free energy changes of the association equilibria have been computed.

WE have already reported¹⁻³ that the rate of solvolytic aquation of chloropentaamminecobalt(III) ion is significantly accelerated in the presence of bivalent anions, sulphate¹, maleate and phthalate² and oxalate³. The rate accelerating influence has been attributed to the formation of more labile chloropentaamminecobalt(III)-anion ion-pairs. The release of chloride ion from the ion-pairs has been shown to take place by (i) aquation of the ion-pairs, (ii) interchange reaction between the inner sphere chloride ion and the outer sphere associating anion. As a sequel to these studies, the present communication deals with the study of the catalytic action of malonate and succinate anions on the acid hydrolysis reaction of chloropentaamminecobalt(III) ion in order to examine the effect of size and basicity of ion-pairing anion and the effect, specific to the anion, on the rate accelerating ability.

Experimental

Preparation of the complexes: Chloropentaamminecobalt(III) perchlorate, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}](\text{ClO}_4)_2$, was prepared and purified as described previously^{1,4}. The purity of the sample was checked by estimating the chloride and cobalt contents of the complex. (Found: Co, 15.35; Cl, 9.3 per cent. Calc. for $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}](\text{ClO}_4)_2$: Co, 15.57; Cl, 9.4 per cent.)

The measured molar absorptivity ($\text{Cm}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1}$) of 50.5 at 532 nm agrees well with the value of 50.5 reported in the literature⁵.

Aquopentaamminecobalt(III) perchlorate $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{H}_2\text{O}](\text{ClO}_4)_3$, was prepared and purified as described previously^{1,2,6}. The measured molar absorptivity of $\epsilon_{492} = 47.8$ is in fair agreement with the values of $\epsilon_{492} = 47.7^5$ and $\epsilon_{491} = 47.3^6$ reported previously.

Malonate - pentaamminecobalt(III) perchlorate $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{C}_3\text{H}_3\text{O}_4](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and succinato-pentaamminecobalt(III) perchlorate, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{O}_4](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ were prepared and purified as described in literature⁷.

(Found: Co, 13.25 per cent. Calc. for $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{C}_3\text{H}_3\text{O}_4](\text{ClO}_4)_2$: Co, 13.22 per cent.)

(Found: Co, 12.65 per cent. Calc. for $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{O}_4](\text{ClO}_4)_2$: Co, 12.80 per cent.)

The measured molar absorptivities for malonato- and succinato-pentaamminecobalt(III) complexes at 500 nm were 74.25 and 67.5 respectively,

The sodium salts of malonic and succinic acids were prepared by mixing together requisite amounts of sodium hydroxide and the acids of known concentration. Reagent grade sodium perchlorate was used for adjusting ionic strength. Double distilled water was used for preparing all solutions. Perchloric acid and other chemicals were of reagent quality.

Kinetic experiments: Aquation rate studies and product analysis were carried out as described earlier^{1,2}.

Results

The pseudo first-order rate constants for the release of chloride ion from the complex were derived from the slopes of the plots of $\log(v_\infty - v_t)$ vs. time 't', where v_t is the volume of silver nitrate consumed after time 't', v_∞ being the volume calculated for the total coordinated chloride. The results obtained are collected in Table 1.

TABLE I—ACID HYDROLYSIS OF $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}](\text{CLO}_4)_2$ IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION IN THE PRESENCE OF MALONATE (MAL^{2-}) AND SUCCINATE (SUCC^{2-}) ANIONS.

Concentration of the complex = $5 \times 10^{-3} M$.			Ionic strength = $0.3 M$.					
$[\text{HCLO}_4] \times 10^3 M.$	$[\text{HL}^-] \times 10^3 M.$	$[\text{L}^{2-}] \times 10^3 M.$	$k_{obs} \times 10^5 / \text{sec}^{(a)}$			$k_{ip} \times 10^5 / \text{sec}$		
			40°	45°	50°	40°	45°	50°
10	—	—	1.02	1.87	3.36	—	—	—
..	5(NaHMal)	5(Na_2 Mal)	1.16	2.10	3.60	2.31	4.08	6.05
..	10(NaHMal)	10(Na_2 Mal)	1.28	2.30	3.81	2.29	4.06	6.08
..	20(NaHMal)	20(Na_2 Mal)	1.46	2.60	4.13	2.31	4.06	6.06
..	30(NaHMal)	30(Na_2 Mal)	1.59	2.81	—	2.30	4.07	—
						(32.2)	(29.5)	(24.1)
..	5(NaHSucc)	5(Na_2 Succ)	1.17	2.13	3.62	2.30	4.54	6.38
..	10(NaHSucc)	10(Na_2 Succ)	1.29	2.34	3.83	2.36	4.51	6.36
..	20(NaHSucc)	20(Na_2 Succ)	1.47	2.67	4.18	2.33	4.50	6.39
..	30(NaHSucc)	30(Na_2 Succ)	1.59	2.94	—	2.33	4.56	—
..	50(NaHSucc)	50(Na_2 Succ)	1.78	3.26	—	2.36	4.51	—
						(28.4)	(24.0)	(20.35)

a. The observed rate constants are accurate upto ± 1 per cent. The ' k_{ip} ' values are given in the parantheses at the end of each system under k_{ip} readings.

The acid hydrolysis rate constants of the free complex ion have been determined at 40°, 45° and 50°. The interaction of the free complex ion with the added dicarboxylate anions is presumed to result in the formation of outer sphere complexes or ion-pairs of the type, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}^{2+}, \text{L}^{2-}]$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}^{2+}, \text{HL}^-]^+$, where L^{2-} and HL^- stand for the bivalent and univalent anions respectively. The observed rate constant would, therefore, be a composite term consisting of the rate constant for the aquation of the free complex ion and the equilibrium constants and rate constants for the formation and aquation of the ion-pairs. The results were analysed as described in our earlier publication¹. The calculation of the rate constants utilising the following equations,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-dc}{dt} = k_{obs} \times c = k_1[\text{Cp}^{2+}] + k_{ip} [\text{CpL}] \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs} - k_1} = \frac{1}{k_{ip} - k_1} + \frac{1}{(k_{ip} - k_1) k_{ip} [\text{L}^{2-}]_f} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

and

$$[\text{L}^{2-}]_f = \frac{[\text{L}^{2-}]_T}{1 + \frac{[\text{HL}^-]_t}{[\text{L}^{2-}]_t} + \frac{k_{ip} c}{1 + k_{ip} [\text{L}^{2-}]_f} + k_{As} [\text{Na}^+]_T} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Scheme I

was done by an iterative procedure using the IBM 1130 computer^{1,2}. The k_{ip} and k_{ip} values have been recorded in Table 1.

Product distribution : The possible path-ways for the formation of $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{H}_2\text{O}^{3+}$, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{L}]^+$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{L}]^+$ have been delineated below (Scheme 1).

The release of chloride ion, according to scheme-I, takes place through three path-ways (k_1 , k'_{ip} and $k_{3(ip)}$). $k_{3(ip)}$ was calculated in the same manner as reported previously^{1,2}, using the equations,

$$\begin{aligned} D_t = & E_1 A_0 e^{-k_{obs} t} + \frac{E_2 A_0 k_{obs}}{k_2 - k_{obs}} (e^{-k_{obs} t} - e^{-k_2 t}) \\ & + E_3 \frac{A_0 k_{obs} e^{-k_2 t}}{k_2 - k_{obs}} - \frac{k_2 A_0 e^{-k_{obs} t}}{k_2 - k_{obs}} \\ & - \frac{k_{3(ip)} A_0 e^{-k_{obs} t}}{k_{obs}} + \frac{A_0 k_{3(ip)}}{k_{obs}} + A_0 \quad \dots \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$k_{3(ip)} = \frac{k_{3(ip)}^0 k_{ip} [L^{2-}]_f}{1 + k_{ip} [L^{2-}]_f} \dots \dots \dots (8)$$

where each term has its usual meaning^{1,2}. The k_2 , $k_{3(ip)}$ and $k_{3(ip)}^0$ values have been recorded in Table 2.

Computation of activation and thermodynamic parameters :

The activation parameters, ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger for the reaction paths k_1 , k_{ip} and $k_{3(ip)}^0$ and the thermodynamic parameters for the association process involving $Co(NH_3)_5Cl^{2+}$ ion and malonate and succinate anions were calculated by the procedures described previously¹. The data have been collected in Table 3.

The thermodynamic stability of the inner sphere chelates are known to decrease⁸ with increase in ring size. The extent to which this effect would persist for outer sphere complexes was put to test in this work. It is evident from the results that the stability of the ion-pairs attains a limiting value for the bivalent anions even though the ring size is altered to a large extent (oxalate⁸, malonate and succinate⁹, maleate and phthalate²). The k_{ip} values for oxalate, malonate and succinate are not commensurate with the order of basicity and size of the dicarboxylates (the ion-pair rate constants are 4.60×10^{-6} /sec, 5.14×10^{-6} /sec and 5.03×10^{-6} /sec respectively for oxalate, malonate and succinate ion-pairs at 25°, the second dissociation constants of the corresponding acids being 2.66×10^{-4} , 8.45×10^{-6} and 1.03×10^{-5} at the same temperature).

A predominantly electrostatic process is visualised to account for the enhanced reactivity of the ion-pairs by

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE k_{ip} , k_2 , $k_{3(ip)}$ AND $k_{3(ip)}^0$ PATHS OF REACTION.

System	[L ²⁻]x 10 ³ M.	Path-way	Temp. (°C)					
			40	45	50			
Malonate	1.00 2.00 4.00 6.00	$k_{ip} \times 10^5$ /sec	2.30 ± 0.02	4.06 ± 0.02	6.06 ± 0.02			
		$k_2 \times 10^4$ /sec	1.12	2.10	3.83			
		$k_{3(ip)}$ × 10 ⁶ /sec						
			0.30 ± 0.08	0.60 ± 0.07	0.98 ± 0.09			
			0.43 ± 0.09	0.92 ± 0.07	1.40 ± 0.13			
	Succinate	1.00 2.00 4.00 6.00		0.52 ± 0.08	1.23 ± 0.09	—		
			$k_{3(ip)}^0 \times 10^6$ /sec	0.73 ± 0.07	1.67 ± 0.10	2.61 ± 0.13		
			$k_{ip} \times 10^5$ /sec			2.34 ± 0.02	4.52 ± 0.03	6.38 ± 0.02
				1.12	2.10	3.85		
			$k_{3(ip)}$ × 10 ⁶ /sec					
			0.47 ± 0.08	0.55 ± 0.08	1.00 ± 0.12			
			0.52 ± 0.10	0.64 ± 0.09	1.31 ± 0.09			
			0.66 ± 0.09	0.91 ± 0.10	1.60 ± 0.09			
		$k_{3(ip)}$ × 10 ⁶ /sec	0.78 ± 0.03	1.02 ± 0.06	1.97 ± 0.14			

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE k_1 , k_{ip} AND $k_{3(ip)}^0$ PATHS OF REACTION AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE ION-ASSOCIATION PROCESS.

System	k_1 path		k_{ip} path			$k_{3(ip)}^0$ path			Ion-association Process			
	ΔH^\ddagger kcal/ mole	ΔS^\ddagger e.u.	ΔG^\ddagger kcal/ mole (40°)	ΔH^\ddagger kcal/ mole	ΔS^\ddagger e.u.	ΔG^\ddagger kcal/ mole (40°)	ΔH^\ddagger kcal/ mole	ΔS^\ddagger e.u.	ΔG^\ddagger kcal/ mole (40°)	ΔH kcal/ mole	ΔS e.u.	ΔG kcal/ mole (40°)
Free ion	23.4 ± 0.2	-6.7 ± 0.6	25.5	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Malonate	—	—	—	17.9 ± 0.15	-22.6 ± 0.48	24.97 ± 0.01	22.00 ± 0.20	-16.5 ± 3.82	27.7	-5.5 ± 0.6	-10.5 ± 1.8	-2.2
Succinate	—	—	—	18.4 ± 0.16	-21.0 ± 0.49	24.97 ± 0.01	22.29 ± 1.30	-15.42 ± 4.1	27.7	-5.7 ± 0.5	-11.6 ± 1.6	-2.1

Discussion

The results (Table 1) reveal that the rate of acid hydrolysis of chloropentaamminecobalt(III) ion is significantly accelerated in the presence of added malonate and succinate anions. The rate accelerating influence is attributed to the formation of more labile ion-pairs. The increase in the rate constant with increase in anion concentration is due to the increased production of ion-pairs, which ultimately attains a constant value. This is reflected in the levelling off of the rate profile.

way of reduction of the overall charge of the complex, which favours the expulsion of chloride ion by a dissociative mechanism. The low negative entropies of activation (vide Table 3), characteristic of such a process in the transition state, are diagnostic of an S_N1 pathway¹⁰ proceeding through an incipient tetragonal pyramid intermediate.

The extent of chloride release through $k_{3(ip)}^0$ path is limited to 7 per cent in the maximum of the total

chloride release (k_1 , k'_{ip} and $k_{3(ip)}^o$ path-ways taken together). The rate constants for the formation of malonato- and succinato-pentaamminecobalt (III) complexes through $k_{3(ip)}^o$ path are calculated to be $1.17 \times 10^{-7}/\text{sec}$ and $1.22 \times 10^{-7}/\text{sec}$ respectively at 25° . The rate constants for the formation of such complexes by anation of the corresponding aquo-carboxylate ion-pairs is $1.30 \times 10^{-6}/\text{sec}$ for both the systems^{2,11} at 25° . The values indicate that only 9.1 per cent of malonato- and 9.4 per cent of succinato-pentaamminecobalt(III) complexes are formed by the $k_{3(ip)}^o$ path compared to the $k_{2(ip)}$ path. It may, therefore, be concluded that the chloride release proceeds predominantly through the formation of the aquo complex. At 510 nm, the molar absorptivities of the chloro-, aquo- and carboxylatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes were found to be 45, 47, 75 and 45, 47, 68 for malonate and succinate systems respectively. The minima in the optical density vs. time plots^{1,2,12} lead us to believe that the formation of the carboxylato-complexes predominantly takes place through the anation of the intermediate aquo-carboxylate ion-pairs (K_2 path). The excellent agreement between the experimental O. D. and the O. D., calculated using the scheme-I supports this conclusion.

The k'_{ip} values for the malonate and succinate systems⁹ are found to be $5.02 \times 10^{-6}/\text{sec}$ and

$4.91 \times 10^{-6}/\text{sec}$ respectively. No conclusion regarding any effect, specific to the added anions, even if present, can be drawn from such data.

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